

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36

Mojiang mine, RaTG13, miners' disease, and related samples remain essential clues in the SARS-CoV-2 origin investigation

Monali C. Rahalkar^{1*} and Rahul A. Bahulikar²

¹C2, Bioenergy group (former Microbial Sciences Division), MACS Agharkar Research Institute, G.G. Agarkar Road, Pune 411004, Maharashtra, India

²BAIF Development Research Foundation, Central Research Station, Urulikanchan, Pune 412202

Tel: +91-20-25325119

Fax: +91-20-2651542

*Corresponding author: monalirahalkar@aripune.org

Keywords: SARS-CoV-2; Mojiang; miners; pneumonia; COVID-19; origin

Conflict of interest statement

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest

Author contribution statement

MCR and RAB conceived the article. MCR and RAB both wrote the article and approved the final version.

Keywords

SARS-CoV-2, Mojiang, miners, Pneumonia, COVID-19, origin

37 **Abstract:**

38

39 We had published an article about the link between the Mojiang mineshaft, RaTG13, and the miners'
40 disease in a perspective article. This paper gained a lot of attention in the question of the COVID-19
41 origin. The miners' pneumonia resembled COVID-19 in many aspects on retrospective analysis.
42 Recently, an article was published by Frutos et al. 2021, which tried to make a point that the miners
43 did not have SARS-CoV-2 infection, and hence they tried to debunk the lab origin of the virus. In the
44 present opinion article, we show the flaws in the interpretation and analysis of Frutos et al. 2021.. We
45 also discuss how WIV shared the information about the mine, miners and RaTG13 in an incomplete
46 and delayed manner. Many of the journalists attempts to visit the mineshaft were in vain, as they
47 were not allowed to reach the site. In light of all these events, we also further discuss how the analyses
48 of the samples collected from the mine and miners may offer different answers to the currently
49 unsolved problem of how SARS-CoV-2 originated and the pandemic started in Wuhan.

50

51 **Introduction**

52 It is still a mystery how SARS-COV-2, the virus responsible for the COVID-19 pandemic
53 killing millions and devastating the whole world, appeared in the city of Wuhan, China. As
54 demanded by scientists worldwide, there has to be an in-depth investigation into this matter to
55 prevent subsequent pandemics and for many other reasons (Adidi et al., 2021) (Bloom et al.,
56 2021). A research-related origin of COVID-19 is plausible (Helden et al., 2021). A research-
57 related origin which might have occurred at sampling sites, during transportation, or within the
58 laboratory and might have involved natural, selected, or engineered viruses. For an unbiased
59 investigation, all the pieces of evidence related to SARS-CoV-2 and its related relatives must
60 be studied until there is a clear answer. The natural reservoir and hotspot of SARS-CoV-2 and
61 other SARS-like coronaviruses are horseshoe bats living a thousand miles away from Wuhan
62 in Yunnan, South China, and Guangdong (Latinne et al., 2020).

63 Initially, in a pre-print (Rahalkar and Bahulikar, 2020b) and then published as a perspective
64 article in October 2020 (Rahalkar and Bahulikar, 2020a), we documented a vital clue in the
65 mystery of the origins of SARS-CoV-2. The fact that the closest relative of SARS-CoV-2,
66 RaTG13, was collected from an abandoned mineshaft in Mojiang, Yunnan, in 2013, by Wuhan
67 Institute of Virology (WIV), Wuhan. Our paper also further links the fact that the same mine
68 was the place where six people who went to clean the bat feces had contracted fatal pneumonia,
69 and three of them had died, and the disease was similar to COVID-19.

70 Our present opinion article again focusing on the Mojiang mine has been written for the
71 following purposes: a. Discussion about the interpretations by Frutos et al. article (Frutos et al.,
72 2021) (which tries to disassociate Mojiang mine from the COVID-19 origins mystery) b.
73 Discussion about the late disclosure of facts related to the Mojiang mine by WIV c. Questions
74 about the Mojiang mine being inaccessible to reporters and researchers. In the end, we
75 summarize and give vital suggestions regarding what should be done to the samples and the
76 genomic information which could be obtained from the same, and how it would be necessary
77 in solving the current mystery of the SARS-CoV-2 origins.

78 **A. Discussion about the interpretations by Frutos et al. article (Frutos et al., 2021)**

79 Recently, a paper was published (Frutos et al., 2021) entitled 'Origin of COVID-19: Dismissing
80 the Mojiang mine theory and the laboratory accident narrative'. The authors try to disprove
81 that the miners who worked in a mineshaft in 2012 in Tongguan, Mojiang, Yunnan had a
82 SARS-CoV2 infection. And further, say that the lab leak theory based on the Mojiang mine
83 incident is false. There needs to be a clarification to the hypothesis by (Frutos et al., 2021) that
84 researchers proposed that the miners had COVID-19 or SARS. Neither our paper (Rahalkar
85 and Bahulikar, 2020a) nor the commentary to our paper (Alex, 2021) has proposed that the
86 miners were infected with SARS-CoV-2 and hence had COVID-19. What we have presented
87 in our report is the resemblance between COVID-19 and the miners' pneumonia.

88 **1. Major symptoms, radiological features of the miners pneumonia consistent with**
89 **COVID-19**

90 According to WHO, the most common symptoms listed in COVID-19 are fever, cough,
91 tiredness, very similar to the symptoms reported by the miners [https://www.who.int/health-](https://www.who.int/health-topics/coronavirus#tab=tab_3)
92 [topics/coronavirus#tab=tab_3](https://www.who.int/health-topics/coronavirus#tab=tab_3). Fever (80.4%), fatigue (46%), cough (63.1%), and
93 expectoration (41.8%) were the most common clinical manifestations in a metaanalysis of 3062
94 patients (Zhu et al., 2020). Frutos et al 2021 noted that the less common symptoms in COVID-
95 19 such as digestive signs, headache, etc. (Zhu et al., 2020) were absent in the miners, but these
96 are not the most typical signs present in all COVID-19 patients (Huang et al., 2020). Secondly,
97 the cough in COVID-19 is dry and also productive as expectoration has also been commonly
98 observed (41.8% cases) (Zhu et al., 2020). The third point is about the radiological features
99 compared in the miner patients and COVID-19 patients. The most common findings in the CT
100 scans in COVID-19 patients are ground-glass opacities, consolidation, and bilateral
101 involvement of the lungs (Huang et al., 2020) (Kwee and Kwee, 2020). All of these main
102 features were seen in the CT scans of the miners especially of patients 2, 3 and 4, which were
103 the most serious cases, worked in the mine for a longer time. The differences highlighted by
104 Frutos et al 2021 were mainly the mediastinal lymphadenopathies, present in majority of the
105 miners. Though mediastinal lymphadenopathies or lymph node enlargement were not initially
106 considered a typical feature as said by Frutos 2021, a French study published in April 2020, in
107 the Lancet, documents that 66% of the critically ill cases had this condition, and it may be
108 associated with serious COVID-19 patients (Valette et al., 2020). Similarly, pleural effusion
109 has also been observed in critically ill COVID-19 cases (Zhan et al., 2021). The radiological
110 features of the miners' pneumonia had also been inspected by an expert radiologist in Pune,
111 India, who was already examining several COVID-19 X-rays and CT scans daily (June 2020).
112 His opinion was: 'Most of the cases (patients 2, 3 and 4) have following findings. 1. Diffuse

113 ground-glass opacities. 2. Peripheral subpleural ground-glass opacities. 3. Some areas of
114 peripheral consolidation. These findings are consistent with what we see nowadays in Covid-
115 19. Consolidation can be due to superadded infection in these patients, bacterial fungal, etc.’

116 **2. IgG antibodies to SARS-like coronaviruses:**

117 One of the essential contradictions in the miners’ incident is the positive IgG antibodies to
118 SARS-like viruses, documented in Chapter 3 of Canping Huang’s PhD thesis (Huang, 2016)
119 [https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/20694207-canping-huang-phd-novel-virus-](https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/20694207-canping-huang-phd-novel-virus-discovery-in-bat-isn-translation)
120 [discovery-in-bat-isn-translation](https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/20694207-canping-huang-phd-novel-virus-discovery-in-bat-isn-translation). Four of the four tested patients from the mine incident had
121 IgG Ab to SARS-like viruses. Frutos et al. 2021 have not taken into consideration these positive
122 IgG antibody tests in their analysis. Huang Canping was a student of George Gao, the present
123 director for China Centre for disease control and prevention. On the contrary, WIV reported in
124 the addendum that the 13 samples they had did not show any positive Ab for SARS-like or
125 SARS-CoV-2 infections. It is also surprising that they have preserved the samples for eight
126 years. With respect to the controversy, Dr. Gao was interviewed this year by the France2
127 channel for their documentary, and he was asked about this particular incident and the IgG
128 antibodies in the four patients. According to him, the miners showed positive IgG for SARS-
129 like coronavirus infection, but he could not pinpoint if the infection was from the mine or earlier
130 or by a new virus [documentary: [https://www.francetvinfo.fr/sante/maladie/coronavirus/video-](https://www.francetvinfo.fr/sante/maladie/coronavirus/video-coronavirus-le-mystere-des-origines_4328629.html)
131 [coronavirus-le-mystere-des-origines_4328629.html](https://www.francetvinfo.fr/sante/maladie/coronavirus/video-coronavirus-le-mystere-des-origines_4328629.html) (Vilar, 2021), 11th March 2021, 18.3 minutes
132 onwards]. The positive tests were documented in Huang Canping’s Ph.D. thesis in 2016, long
133 before the pandemic, and hence should be unbiased in contrast to the addendum which was
134 presented 11 months after the pandemic. Also, the confirmation of the positive Ab test in the
135 four miners by Dr. George Gao in a French documentary is significant.

136 **3. Opinion of Dr. Zhong Nanshan about the serious miners: Primary viral pneumonia**

137 Frutos et al. 2021 study does not take into consideration the diagnosis by Dr. Zhong Nanshan,
138 one of the most prominent pulmonologists in China. Dr. Zhong Nanshan was consulted by
139 video-conferencing on 19th June 2012, who had examined all the reports and had suggested
140 that the two miners admitted (patients 3 and 4) had interstitial pneumonia, a high possibility of
141 virus infection, and secondary infection in the form of invasive pulmonary aspergillosis. He
142 had asked the doctors to send a throat swab for detection of SARS-like viruses and asked to do
143 a SARS-Ab test to be carried out in WIV. He also suggested using antifungals for secondary
144 fungal infections and using a broncho-scope to clear out the mucus (Xu, 2013) (Page 33
145 translation). As he was the most prominent doctor during the SARS outbreak in 2002-2003,
146 his opinion about investigating which types of horseshoe bats were present in the Mojiang mine
147 suggests that he suspected the illness due to SARS-like coronaviruses. Also, the testing of
148 throat swabs and antibodies against SARS or SARS-like coronaviruses is suggestive that he
149 thought that the patients had an infection due to a SARS-like coronavirus arising from the
150 horseshoe bats, which also happens to be the conclusion of the Master's thesis by Li Xu.

151 **B. Discussion about the late disclosure of facts related to the Mojiang mine by WIV**

152 **1. Addendum to Zhou et al 2020 confirmed Mojiang mine incident (Nov 2020)**

153 After one month of the publication of our article (Rahalkar and Bahulikar, 2020a), an
154 Addendum was published by Shi Zhengli and others (Zhou et al., 2020a). Here, they declared
155 for the first time that WIV had been sampling the Mojiang mineshaft for a total of three years,
156 from 2012-2015. Shi Zhengli and her colleagues had suspected that the miners had been
157 infected by an unknown virus, and hence they sampled bats, rats, and musk shrews in and
158 around the cave (Zhou et al., 2020a). Out of a total of 1322 samples collected, they detected
159 293 diverse coronaviruses, which included a total of 9 SARS-like coronaviruses, including
160 RaTG13 (Zhou et al., 2020a). The eight SARS-like coronaviruses were not reported in their
161 pre-pandemic and post-pandemic papers (Ge et al., 2016) (Zhou et al., 2020b). They also admit

162 that they had analyzed 13 serum samples collected between July and October 2012 from four
163 of the patients (miners), of which one was deceased who showed severe respiratory disease.
164 However, neither did they publish the rest partial or complete sequences of these eight SARS-
165 like coronaviruses nor disclosed their sequence ids (Zhou et al., 2020a). Also, the Addendum
166 did not reveal any detailed information of the 2012 miners' pneumonia.

167 **2. SARS-CoV-2, RaTG15, RaTG13 and seven other coronaviruses from the mine form**
168 **Clade 4 (May and Dec 2021)**

169 A manuscript co-written by Shi Zhengli and Peter Daszak and published in 2020 (Latinne et
170 al., 2020) does not document that the eight SARS-like coronaviruses (ids 7909, 7896, etc.)
171 were from the Mojiang mineshaft, and only 'Yunnan' is mentioned. In May 2021, after 1.5
172 years of the pandemic, Shi Zhengli published a pre-print saying that eight more viruses are in
173 the same clade as SARS-CoV-2 and RaTG13, all collected from the Tongguan, Mojiang mine.
174 The sample 7909 (Latinne et al., 2020) was renamed RaTG15, and a peer-reviewed paper was
175 published (Guo et al., 2021) after ~2 years of the pandemic. However, it is surprising that
176 though they mentioned these viruses in 2021, they were working on some of these viruses
177 before the pandemic. A Master's thesis done under the guidance of Shi Zhengli, from 2019
178 (Yu, 2019) [https://drive.google.com/file/d/15SwZtLaX20iq1BQvFRpSqiYd4xi-](https://drive.google.com/file/d/15SwZtLaX20iq1BQvFRpSqiYd4xi-UOG8/view?usp=sharing)
179 [UOG8/view?usp=sharing](https://drive.google.com/file/d/15SwZtLaX20iq1BQvFRpSqiYd4xi-UOG8/view?usp=sharing) already mentions the sequencing of a few (7909, 7896, etc.), making
180 it clear that many samples from the Tongguan mine in Mojiang were being studied in WIV.
181 The WHO report on COVID-19 origins [https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/who-](https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/who-convened-global-study-of-origins-of-sars-cov-2-china-part)
182 [convened-global-study-of-origins-of-sars-cov-2-china-part](https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/who-convened-global-study-of-origins-of-sars-cov-2-china-part) also lacks any comments on the
183 miners incident except a line saying 'WIV researchers think that the miners died due to a fungus
184 in the mine', a fact also discussed in the commentary to our article (Alex, 2021). Also, in the
185 WHO report Annex, Shi Zhengli mentioned that Clade 4 (consisting of SARS-CoV-2,
186 RaTG13, RaTG15, etc.) is specific for Yunnan. The question is why none of these sequences

187 were published pre-pandemic or immediately after the pandemic. To conclude, many crucial
188 facts regarding RaTG13, RaTG15 and the Mojiang mine were not disclosed by WIV in a timely
189 manner which would have been essential with respect to the question of how the virus
190 originated. Hence, as recently expressed in an opinion piece (Vineis and Salmaso, 2021), the
191 case is still open.

192 **C. Mojiang Mine, inaccessible and closed for reporters and researchers:**

193 Access to the Mojiang mine, at the center of everyone's attention, has been entirely denied by
194 China. Reporters from the Associated Press news (KANG et al., 2020), BBC (Sudworth, 2020),
195 France2 (Vilar, 2021), and WSJ (Page et al., 2021) could not reach the area because of
196 roadblocks and secret police in late 2020 and 2021. If there is nothing to hide, why the access
197 to the mine has been closed is a big question.

198

199 **Summary and future suggestions:**

200 1. WIV, Wuhan collected coronavirus samples including SARS-like coronaviruses from the
201 Mojiang mine, an abandoned mine in Yunnan, Southern China, including RaTG13, one of the
202 nearest neighbors of SARS-CoV-2 and eight more from the clade.

203 2. The same mine in Tongguan, Mojiang was the place where six people went to clean the bat
204 guano, fell ill with severe pneumonia, and three of them died, 2012. The miners' pneumonia
205 and complications were probably caused by SARS-like coronaviruses in horseshoe bats in the
206 mine, as concluded in the Masters' thesis and as suggested by Dr. Zhong Nanshan. It mostly
207 resembled COVID-19 on retrospective analysis done by us, although we never claimed before
208 or here that it was COVID-19.

209 3. We had never proposed any 'Mojiang miners theory', but just showed the connections of the
210 miners' pneumonia incident and RaTG13 to WIV, Wuhan, the city, where the pandemic started.

211 WIV visited the mines and brought 1322 samples from the mine in their visits from 2012-2015
212 and analyzed serum samples from the miners, but the world does not have access to the
213 information of these samples, as the databases from WIV have been offline since September
214 2019 (Anon et al., 2021). Also, they have at least 13 serum samples from the miners who got
215 severely ill since 2012 till date, and these should be submitted to international researchers.

216 4. We suggest that all the samples from the miners (serum samples, throat swabs, etc.) should
217 be given to a third-party international research laboratory, and metagenomic data from all these
218 samples would clarify the situation, as suggested (Alex, 2021). It would be important to know
219 if any of the samples from the mines or miners had the progenitor of the virus which could
220 have either infected the lab worker or was studied and got released by accident.

221 5. Also, all the information in the databases and computers about the samples and sequencing
222 done, especially on the Mojiang mine samples and the miners' samples, should be opened to
223 the international community for scrutiny.

224 6. Any kind of experiments using RaTG13 or other coronavirus samples collected from the
225 mine should be revealed. This is important as WIV was doing extensive genetic engineering
226 work on SARS-like coronaviruses (Hu et al., 2017).

227 7. The Mojiang mine should be opened to international researchers for sampling with proper
228 PPE kits and precautions taking into consideration that it has SARS-like coronaviruses and the
229 sequences of the viruses can be compared with SARS-CoV-2.

230 **Acknowledgments:**

231 We would like to thank TheSeeker268 and Francisco de Asis for finding the Masters thesis by
232 Yu Ping and for providing the google drive link with the thesis.

233 **Conflicts of Interests:**

234 There are no conflicts of interests.

235 **Translations**

236 Master's thesis (Xu, 2013) [https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/6981198-Analysis-of-](https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/6981198-Analysis-of-Six-Patients-With-Unknown-Viruses.html)
237 [Six-Patients-With-Unknown-Viruses.html](https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/6981198-Analysis-of-Six-Patients-With-Unknown-Viruses.html),

238 Ph.D. thesis (Huang, 2016) [https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/20694207-canping-](https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/20694207-canping-huang-phd-novel-virus-discovery-in-bat-isn-translation)
239 [huang-phd-novel-virus-discovery-in-bat-isn-translation](https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/20694207-canping-huang-phd-novel-virus-discovery-in-bat-isn-translation).

240

241

242

243 **References:**

- 244 Adidi, P., Bahulikar, R., and Butler, C. (2021). "Call for a Comprehensive Investigation of the Origin of
245 SARS-CoV-2, if Possible with Chinese Government Participation". (DOI:
246 10.13140/RG.2.2.21927.27042/1).
- 247 Alex, S. (2021). Commentary: Lethal Pneumonia Cases in Mojiang Miners (2012) and the Mineshaft
248 Could Provide Important Clues to the Origin of SARS-CoV-2. *Frontiers in Public Health* doi:
249 10.3389/fpubh.2021.702199. doi: doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2021.702199.
- 250 Anon, Bostickson, B., and Demaneuf, G. (2021). An investigation into the WIV databases that were
251 taken offline. *DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28029.08160*.
- 252 Bloom, J.D., Chan, Y.A., Baric, R.S., Bjorkman, P.J., Cobey, S., Deverman, B.E., et al. (2021). Investigate
253 the origins of COVID-19. *Science* 372(6543), 694-694. doi: 10.1126/science.abj0016 %J
254 Science.
- 255 Frutos, R., Javelle, E., Barberot, C., Gavotte, L., Tissot-Dupont, H., and Devaux, C.A. (2021). Origin of
256 COVID-19: Dismissing the Mojiang mine theory and the laboratory accident narrative.
257 *Environment Research* 112141.
- 258 Ge, X.Y., Wang, N., Zhang, W., Hu, B., Li, B., Zhang, Y.Z., et al. (2016). Coexistence of multiple
259 coronaviruses in several bat colonies in an abandoned mineshaft. *Viral Sin* 31(1), 31-40. doi:
260 10.1007/s12250-016-3713-9.
- 261 Guo, H., Hua, B., Si, H.-R., Zhu, Y., Zhang, W., Zhou, P., et al. (2021). Identification of a novel lineage
262 bat SARS-related coronaviruses that use bat ACE2 receptor. *Emerging Microbes & Infections*
263 10, 1507-1513.
- 264 Helden, J.v., Colin D Butler, Achaz, G., Bruno Canard, Casane, D., Claverie, J.-M., et al. (2021). An
265 appeal for an objective, open, and transparent scientific debate about the origin of SARS-
266 CoV-2. *The Lancet* 398(10309), 1402-1404.
- 267 Hu, B., Zeng, L.P., Yang, X.L., Ge, X.Y., Zhang, W., Li, B., et al. (2017). Discovery of a rich gene pool of
268 bat SARS-related coronaviruses provides new insights into the origin of SARS coronavirus.
269 *PLoS Pathog* 13(11), e1006698. doi: 10.1371/journal.ppat.1006698.

270 Huang, C. (2016). *Novel virus discovery in bat and the exploration of receptor of bat coronavirus*
271 *HKU9*. PhD.

272 Huang, C., Wang, Y., Li, X., Ren, L., Zhao, J., Hu, Y., et al. (2020). Clinical features of patients infected
273 with 2019 novel coronavirus in Wuhan, China. *The Lancet* 395(10223), 497-506. doi:
274 10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30183-5.

275 KANG, D., CHENG, M., and MCNEIL, S. 2020. China clamps down in hidden hunt for coronavirus
276 origins. [https://apnews.com/article/united-nations-coronavirus-pandemic-china-only-on-ap-
277 bats-24fbadc58cee3a40bca2ddf7a14d2955](https://apnews.com/article/united-nations-coronavirus-pandemic-china-only-on-ap-bats-24fbadc58cee3a40bca2ddf7a14d2955).

278 Kwee, T.C., and Kwee, R.M. (2020). Chest CT in COVID-19: What the Radiologist Needs to Know.
279 *RadioGraphics* 40, 1848-1865. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1148/rg.2020200159>.

280 Latinne, A., Hu, B., Olival, K.J., Zhu, G., Zhang, L., Li, H., et al. (2020). Origin and cross-species
281 transmission of bat coronaviruses in China. *Nature Communications* 11(4235).

282 Page, J., McKay, B., and Hinshaw, D. 2021. The Wuhan Lab Leak Question: A Disused Chinese Mine
283 Takes Center Stage [https://www.wsj.com/articles/wuhan-lab-leak-question-chinese-mine-
284 covid-pandemic-11621871125](https://www.wsj.com/articles/wuhan-lab-leak-question-chinese-mine-covid-pandemic-11621871125).

285 Rahalkar, M.C., and Bahulikar, R.A. (2020a). Lethal Pneumonia Cases in Mojiang Miners (2012) and
286 the Mineshaft Could Provide Important Clues to the Origin of SARS-CoV-2. *Frontiers in Public*
287 *Health* 8(638). doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2020.581569.

288 Rahalkar, M.C., and Bahulikar, R.A. (2020b). "Understanding the origin of 'BatCoVraTG13', a virus
289 closest to SARS-CoV-2".).

290 Sudworth, J. 2020. Covid: Wuhan scientist would 'welcome' visit probing lab leak theory.
291 <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-china-55364445>.

292 Valette, X., Cheyron, D.d., and Goursaud, S. (2020). Mediastinal lymphadenopathy in patients with
293 severe COVID-19. *The Lancet* 20.
294 [https://www.francetvinfo.fr/sante/maladie/coronavirus/video-coronavirus-le-mystere-des-
295 origines_4328629.html](https://www.francetvinfo.fr/sante/maladie/coronavirus/video-coronavirus-le-mystere-des-origines_4328629.html) (Year). Directed by Vilar, V. France: France2.

296 Vineis, P., and Salmaso, S. (2021). The Origin of SARS-CoV-2: Why it matters? *Frontiers in Public*
297 *Health* 9:719914.

298 Xu, L. (2013). *'The analysis of 6 patients with severe pneumonia caused by unknown viruses'* Masters
299 original thesis in Chinese language, Kunming Medical University, China.

300 Yu, P. (2019). *Geographic Evolution of Bat SARS-related Coronaviruses*. Masters, Chinese Academy of
301 Sciences.

302 Zhan, N., Guo, Y., Tian, S., Huang, B., Tian, X., Zou, J., et al. (2021). Clinical characteristics of COVID-19
303 complicated with pleural effusion. *BMC Infectious Diseases* 21(176), 1-10.

304 Zhou, P., Yang, X., Wang, X., and al., e. (2020a). Addendum: A pneumonia outbreak associated with a
305 new coronavirus of probable bat origin. *Nature* 588([https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-
306 2951-z](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2951-z)).

307 Zhou, P., Yang, X.L., Wang, X.G., Hu, B., Zhang, L., Zhang, W., et al. (2020b). A pneumonia outbreak
308 associated with a new coronavirus of probable bat origin. *Nature* 579(7798), 270-273. doi:
309 10.1038/s41586-020-2012-7.

310 Zhu, J., Ji, P., Pang, J., Zhong, Z., Li, H., He, C., et al. (2020). Clinical characteristics of 3062 COVID-19
311 patients: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Medicinal Virology* 92(10), 1902-1914. doi:
312 10.1002/jmv.25884.

313